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Study of Thermal Analytical Characteristics of a New Type of Semi-Liquid Surkov Oil Composition using Modern Innovative Technologies

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Abstract: *This scientific article presents the thermoanalytical analysis of semi-liquid oil composition, tar in the oil, deparaffinized oil, salomas and TSD-7 compound obtained on the basis of local raw materials in our country. In addition, the scientific basis for the production of components of semi-liquid lubricating oils and the evaluation of their ability to work effectively in a high-temperature environment, as well as the graph of thermal analysis of oils, are also widely covered.*

Key words: *thermoanalytical analysis, endothermic temperature, tar, mixture residue, exothermic effect, mass loss, friction, polymorphic change, chemical composition, exploitation.*

Currently, in the production of modern lubricating oils, great importance is attached to the research of their thermoanalytical properties, which, in turn, allow to determine the physical changes in the temperature increase in the friction zones. In this case, the evaporation and melting of the components of lubricating oils in the composition, as well as thermal and thermal oxidation processes, are of great importance. Basically, it plays an important role in determining the temperature of polymorphic changes in the composition of lubricating oils, developing the scientific basis for the production of oil components and evaluating their ability to work effectively in a high-temperature environment. Therefore, thermal analysis is of great importance in the development of new innovative technologies for obtaining various types of lubricating oil compositions. Taking these tasks into account, the thermal properties of new product ingredients necessary for the operation of railway transport were studied.

In the thermoanalytical study of the components of the reducer lubricating oil, the following analysis parameters were checked: Differential-thermal analysis (DTA), Thermogravimetric analysis (TG), differential-thermogravimetric analysis (DTG).

Each of the components involved in the composition of the reducer lubricating oil was tested in this way. For example: Tar component (conditional viscosity at 100 °C) -50%; deparaffinized oil

(conditional viscosity at 100 °C) - 48.2%; salomas-1.5% amount; TsD-7 compound in the amount of 0.3%;

TSD-7 coating is an anti-friction, anti-oxidation and anti-corrosion coating, according to its chemical composition, spirit 101 is a 90% solution of dialkyldiphosphate in mineral oil, obtained on the basis of isobutyl and 2-butylhexyl alcohols.

Salamas is a solid oil obtained by hydrogenation of cottonseed oil in production. The essence of the hydrogenation process is that as a result of hydrogen saturation of unsaturated fatty acids in the double bonds of triacylglycerols, they change into saturated fatty acids, and the state of the fat changes from a liquid state to a solid state.

According to the results of the research, the process of preparing the composition of gear oil is divided into the following stages:

- preparation of components (heating and mixing deparaffinized oil with tar);
- addition of anti-friction and anti-oxidation agent TsD-7 as a co-washing dispersing component;
- by mixing a 40% aqueous solution of NaOH as a thickener at a temperature of 128-130 °C for 3 hours in a mixer (to dehydrate and saponify the mixture);
- cooling of the obtained composition;

The obtained composition with its physico-chemical and operational indicators corresponds to the OSp-reductor oil produced in Russia that meets the TU 38.402-58-81-94 and the OSpUz gear oil that meets the technical requirements of the Republic of Uzbekistan TSh 39.3-225: 2012.

The thermal analysis was recorded using the Paulik-Paulik-Erdey system in the derivatography at a speed of 10 degrees/min and with a 0.128-0.134 gram lead in the sensitivity parameters of the galvanometer T-1200, TG-200, DTA-1/100, DTA-1/100. The recording was carried out in atmospheric 102 conditions. A corundum crucible without a cover with a diameter of 10 mm served as a holder. Al₂O₃ was used as a reference (The obtained results are shown in Fig. #1).

Figure 1. Thermal analysis of reducer lubricating oil composition graph

The results of the research and their analysis are as follows, the DTA graph of the composition of the reducer lubricating oil was characterized by three endothermic effects at 135 °C, 270 °C, 476 °C and two exothermic effects at 415 °C, 607 °C. The first endothermic effect is in the range of 80-140°C, and the mass loss in it is 3.43%, which is due to the transition of the lubricating oil composition from a semi-liquid state to a liquid state. The first exothermic effect is formed in the temperature range of 403-432 °C and is observed with a mass loss of 24.75%. With the endothermic effect at 476 °C and the exothermic effect at 607 °C, 62.3% mass loss is observed. The total mass loss at 600 °C was 72.4%. At the same time (TG and DTG graphs), the maximum rate of mass loss is in the temperature range of 403-493 °C, which is explained by the passage of complex thermooxidation processes, i.e., the result of thermooxidation destruction of soaps obtained in the process of saponification and hydrooxidation on the basis of salomas due to the heating of the reducing oil.

In order to identify the process of thermooxidation of reducer lubricating oil, a separate thermoanalytical analysis of each of its components (ingredients) was carried out. Thermoanalytical analysis of the tar included in the reducer lubricating oil is as follows (presented in Figure 2).

Figure 2. Tar in the reducer oil thermoanalytical analysis

Tar's DTA has two endothermic effects at temperatures of 68 °C and 139 °C and three exothermic effects at 367 °C; 395 °C; and appeared at 550 °C. As endothermic tar at 68 °C softens and turns into a liquid state, the evaporation of volatile (volatile) mixture residues was clearly demonstrated compared to the endothermic effect at 139 °C. In addition, the rate of mass loss increased by 8-12% with an increase in temperature of 104 in the range of 120-200°C was observed in the graph of DTG. 367 °C; 395 °C; and exothermic effects at 550 °C are explained by thermal oxidation processes due to tar heating. The maximum mass loss of tar in the TG graph is in the range of 336-645 °C and its value is 54-56%. It should be noted that, according to the results presented in Fig. 1-2, the temperature increase of tar and reducer oil is different in relation to each other, it is observed at a temperature of 450 °C, where as a result of the reaction, it was observed that the temperature environment of the tar rises to

550 °C, but and in reducer lubricating oil, the exothermic effect shifts to a higher temperature of 607°C, that is, it is observed under the influence of tar and asphaltenes contained in the tar.

DTA of deparaffinized oil was mainly expressed by exothermic effect at the temperature range of 93-310 °C. A weak endothermic effect at 318 °C turns into an exothermic effect at 440 °C. The next exothermic effect was observed in the range of 478-563 °C and at 606 °C.

Figure 3. Thermoanalytical analysis of deparaffinized oil graph is presented

The maximum mass loss in TG is seen in the range of 310-455 °C, i.e. at the highest point (peak) in the DTG graph. It is about more than 90%, and a relatively small variation of 2-4% appears up to 540 °C. Mass loss up to 310 °C is 2-3%. The processes that occur when deparaffinized oil is heated up to 540°C can be represented by thermooxidation processes, unlike tar (presented in Figure 3), it was shown that deparaffinized oil has thermal stability up to 310°C.

Salomas differential thermal analysis is characterized by six exothermic effects, which are 308 °C; 375 °C, 385 °C; At 441 °C, 540 °C and 600 °C, the maximum loss of mass in TG is observed in the temperature range of 220-390 °C up to 8-62%. Endothermic effect 479 °C; observed at 610 °C (presented in Fig. 4). Manifestation of endothermic and exothermic effects in Salomas is observed in various types of thermal oxidations that occur during the decomposition of various unsaturated fatty acids of triacylglycerol in its composition.

Figure 4. Thermoanalytical Analysis of Salomas

DTA of TsD-7 anti-friction and anti-oxidation coating is 240 °C; 336 °C; 468 °C; 540 °C; with an exothermic effect at 270 °C; It is manifested by an endothermic effect at 382 °C and 507 °C.

Figure 5. Thermoanalytical analysis of TsD-7 installation

The mass loss of TsD-7 at TG up to 220 °C was more than 5%. Thermooxidation processes at a temperature higher than 220 °C, the maximum loss of mass according to the TG graph is in the

temperature range of 220 °C-382 °C, which is 57-58.5% (presented in Figure 5). When evaluating the thermooxidation stability of the objects under study, that is, gear oil and its components, attention was paid to the exothermic effect with temperature changes in the DTA graph, the temperature of the loss of 10-50% of the mass at the given temperatures from the thermogravimetric TG was determined in the differential thermogravimetric graph, and the maximum mass loss rate temperatures 107 were determined from the DTG. The high points in the thermogram of DTA were taken as interphase transition temperatures.

A comparative analysis of gear oil and its components shows that the exothermic effect of tar at 367 °C and deparaffinized oil is manifested in the DTA thermogram of gear oil in the temperature range of 403-432 °C. Exothermic effect of tar at 586 °C and deparaffinized oil at 440 °C in the DTA thermogram of gear oil, the maximum mixing temperature of the exothermic effect occurs at 607 °C, indicating that deparaffinized oil and relatively more tar are part of 1.7; 12.0; The thermal relations between tar and asphaltenes in the amount of 7.2% become important. The use of these components as sodium soaps of anti-oxidation saponified salomas product of TsD-7 in the gear oil increases the thermal stability and resistance to thermal decomposition of the gear oil. The increase in the thermal stability temperature of the reducer oil is explained by the shift of the temperature of 10% loss of mass at the given temperature to 380°C-390°C.

At present, nigrol oil is used in the operation of electric locomotives and diesel locomotives by "Uzbekistan temir yollari" JSC at the "Tinchlik" DEPO. According to the results of thermal analysis of this nigrol oil, the DTA graph was characterized by three endothermic effects at 165 °C, 220 °C, 397 °C and two exothermic effects at 397 °C, 598 °C. The first endothermic effect is in the range of 85-120°C, and the mass loss in it is 5.20%, which is due to the transition of the oil from a semi-liquid state to a liquid state. The first exothermic effect occurs in the temperature range of 437-478 °C, and 35.5% mass loss is observed with 108 . 62.3% mass loss is observed with endothermic effect at 397 °C and exothermic effect at 589 °C. The total mass loss at 600 °C was 83.4%. At the same time (TG and DTG graphs), the maximum rate of mass loss is in the temperature range of 437-483 °C, which can be explained by the passage of complex thermooxidation processes, i.e., the liquefaction of nigrol oil at a high temperature is 2 times higher than that of the gear oil (shown in Fig. 5).

The test sample of OSp-Uz-L gear oil was subjected to industrial pilot testing on test and control locomotives of the 3TE10M series #1172, #1306, #1060, and the following acceptable results were achieved:

- OSp-Uz-L reducer gear oil 3TE10M series #1172, #1306, #1060 has increased the cost of materials and its service life under operating conditions. (Premature bending of the teeth of the gear reducer of the transmission part and preservation of its structural elements was observed.)
- it was proved that the new OSp-Uz reducer oil has higher parameters compared to "Nigrol" oil in terms of viscosity and temperature indicators, and it was not observed to accumulate during the period of use, the conditions of use were improved.
- the specificity of OSp-Uz reducer oil reduces the increase in friction due to its mechanical structural properties compared to nigrol oil.
- increased energy consumption during the operation of gears and mechanisms and periodicity of TO-2, TO-2, TR-1 TXK (Maintenance) by 30%.

According to the conclusions obtained from the industrial pilot test, no objections were raised to "Nigrol" oil of the reducer drive oil used in the traction reducer and the gearboxes during the

operation. Temperatures in the lower part of three 3TE10M locomotive cabins were determined during operation according to the order. The temperature at the bottom of the control locomotives was found to be in the range of 37.4 °C -38.6 °C, in the control locomotive it was 33.9 °C -33.1 °C, and they did not exceed the permissible limit of 60 °C, but the mechanical particles in the oil according to the results of the chemical analysis indicating its amount, it was found that its amount increased slightly in the control locomotive.

The test sample of OSp-Uz gear oil on the 3TE10M diesel locomotive has been tested for 10,119 km, 13,880 km, and 15,464 km, as well as the state of maintenance (TXK-3).

So, in the conclusion part, we did not have any objections regarding the performance and technical condition of the OSp-Uz gear oil used in traction reducers and gearboxes during operation. According to the inspection results, samples of OSp-Uz gear oil and nigrol oil were taken for chemical analysis, and the results of chemical analysis were found to be at the required level compared to nigrol oil.

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